

Kinetics and mechanism of the reaction of aquachromium(III) with pyridine-3-carboxylic and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid : A comparative study

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Kinetics of the reactions of pyridine carboxylic acids with aquachromium(III) at 35° have been studied spectrophotometrically as a function of $[Cr^{III}]_T$, $[pyridine\ carboxylic\ acid]_T$, pH and dielectric constant of the medium. The reaction has been monitored at 570 nm. The reaction takes place via an outer-sphere association between Cr^{III} and pyridine carboxylic acid, followed by transformation of the outer-sphere into an inner-sphere complex by slow interchange. The anation rate constants (k_{an}) at 35° and $I = 0.5\ mol\ dm^{-3}$ (KNO_3) and K_{os} (outer-sphere complex formation constants) have been evaluated. The anation reaction of the $Cr(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ follows I_a path.

Substitution reactions of $Cr(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ with various amino acids and other acids have been carried out¹⁻⁵. Anation reactions of $Cr(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ take place at the metal center via a transition state showing a greater degree of bond making with the incoming ligand than of bond breaking with the leaving ligand⁶. In this paper the reactions between $Cr(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ with pyridine-3-carboxylic and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid are reported.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry and reaction products : Addition of acidic aquachromium(III) solution to a solution of pyridine-3-carboxylic or pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acids, resulted in an increase in absorbance in the visible range. The absorption spectra of the mixture (Cr^{III} + pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid $I = 0.5\ mol\ dm^{-3}$) indicate the formation of the complex (Fig. 1). The binding of Cr^{III} with the ligand takes place through the carboxylate as well as through ring (N)⁷. The Job's curve also indicates the formation of a 1 : 1 metal-ligand complexes in both the cases.

Effect of reaction rate on $[H^+]$: The reaction were studied at 35° with pH = 3.0 and 3.5, $[Cr^{III}]_T = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ and $I = 0.5\ mol\ dm^{-3}$ and at various fixed $[H_2A]_T$ ($H_2A =$ pyridine carboxylic acid). Table 1 contains the pertinent data at constant temperature. It is evident that the rate constants increase as the pH increases. To explain the pH dependence on the reaction rate, it is necessary to consider the dissociation equilibrium of H_2A .

With the increase in pH, the concentration of HA^- and A^{2-} increases hence the rate constant increases. The hydrolysis constant (K_h) at 25°⁸ for $Cr(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ is 1.92×10^{-4} , hence, $[(Cr(H_2O)_5OH)^{2+}]$ will be negligibly small at pH = 3.5. The dissociation constants of H_2A at 35° were calculated using ΔH° and ΔS° values⁹ for the pyridine carboxylic acids. The K_{a_1} (35°) value is 8.13×10^{-3} for pyridine-3-carboxylic acid and 7.87×10^{-3} for pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid.

Fig. 1. (a) Structure for the first product, $[Cr^{III}]$ + pyridine-3-carboxylic acid, (b) structure for the second product, $[Cr^{III}]$ + pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid

Effect of reaction rate on pyridine carboxylic acid concentration : The effect of varying $[H_2A]_T$ on the reaction rate was studied at fixed $[H^+]$ and at 35°. The concentration of H_2A was varied from 0.025 to 0.15 $mol\ dm^{-3}$ at fixed $[Cr^{III}]_T = 0.005$ and $I = 0.5\ mol\ dm^{-3}$. The results are presented in Table 1. It is observed that as $[H_2A]$ increases, k_{obs} increases in a non-linear fashion, indicating outer-sphere complexation between the reactant species¹⁰.

Effect of reaction rate on Cr^{III} concentration : In the first set of kinetic experiments, the Cr^{III} concentration was

Table 1. Kinetic data for the anation reaction of Cr^{III} with pyridine-3-carboxylic and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid

Temp. = 35°, I = 0.5 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃)

[Cr ^{III}] mol dm ⁻³	[H ₂ A] mol dm ⁻³	% (v/v) MeOH	pH	k _{obs} 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k _{obs} [*] 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.005	0.025	0	3.5	1.25	4.70
0.005	0.025	5	3.5	1.31	5.81
0.005	0.025	10	3.5	1.41	7.91
0.005	0.025	20	3.5	1.57	8.36
0.005	0.025	30	3.5	2.00	10.6
0.005	0.025	40	3.5	2.42	-
0.004	0.025	0	3.5	1.24	4.67
0.003	0.025	0	3.5	1.31	4.75
0.005	0.030	0	3.5	1.45	5.25
0.005	0.035	0	3.5	1.65	5.91
0.005	0.040	0	3.5	1.96	6.60
0.005	0.045	0	3.5	2.17	7.29
0.005	0.050	0	3.5	2.38	7.60
0.005	0.075	0	3.5	3.13	9.25
0.005	0.100	0	3.5	3.56	9.68
0.005	0.125	0	3.5	3.92	9.83
0.005	0.150	0	3.5	4.25	10.1
0.005	0.025	0	3.0	0.98	3.25
0.005	0.030	0	3.0	1.17	3.82
0.005	0.035	0	3.0	1.33	4.34
0.005	0.040	0	3.0	1.50	4.76
0.005	0.045	0	3.0	1.75	5.26
0.005	0.050	0	3.0	1.92	5.75
0.005	0.075	0	3.0	2.89	7.01
0.005	0.100	0	3.0	3.17	7.34
0.005	0.125	0	3.0	3.34	7.80
0.005	0.150	0	3.0	3.48	8.01

k_{obs} = Nicotinic acid; k_{obs}^{*} = pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid.

varied at fixed pyridine carboxylic acid concentration (0.025 mol dm⁻³). The ionic strength, pH and temperature were kept constant. The pseudo-first order plots were linear, giving 10⁴ k_{obs} = 1.26 ± 0.03 s⁻¹ for nicotinic acid and 4.71 ± 0.03 s⁻¹ for pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (Table 1). The independence of k_{obs} at 35° under the condition [H₂A] = 0.025, I = 0.5 mol dm⁻³ and pH = 3.5 over a [Cr^{III}] range is in agreement with first order dependence of the rate on [Cr^{III}]_T. The rate law is therefore given as

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} \quad (3)$$

Effect of reaction rate on methanol content : In order to determine the influence of dielectric constant of the medium on the reaction rate, the anation reaction was also stud-

ied in methanol-water solvent. An increase in k_{obs} was observed as the dielectric constant (D) of the medium was decreased (Table 1). A plot of log k_{obs} vs 1/D was linear with positive slope indicating that the reacting species have opposite charge. According to Bjerrum equation¹¹ the values of the outer-sphere complex formation constant K_{OS} will increase with the decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium and therefore, outer-sphere complexation is enhanced with a consequent increase in the rate.

The reaction sequence given in Scheme 1 is consistent with the experimental data where O.S (outer-sphere complex) = Cr(H₂O)₆³⁺, HA⁻

Scheme 1

The rate law for the above reaction can be derived in the following manner.

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{an}} [\text{O.S}]_{\text{e}} = k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{OS}} K_{a_1} [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_{\text{e}} \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{e}}}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (8)$$

$$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_{\text{e}} + [\text{O.S}]_{\text{e}} = [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_{\text{e}} / [\text{H}^+] \{ [\text{H}^+] + K_{a_1} \times K_{\text{OS}} [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{e}} \} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{OS}} K_{a_1} [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_{\text{T}} [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{e}}}{[\text{H}^+] + k_{a_1} K_{\text{OS}} [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{e}}} \quad (10)$$

$$[\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{e}} + [\text{HA}^-]_{\text{e}} = [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{e}} + K_{a_1} [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{e}} / [\text{H}^+] \quad (11)$$

$$= [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{e}} \{ ([\text{H}^+] + K_{a_1}) / [\text{H}^+] \} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{OS}} K_{a_1} [\text{Cr}^{3+}]_{\text{T}} [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{H}^+] + K_{a_1} + K_{a_1} K_{\text{OS}} [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{T}}} \quad (13)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{OS}} K_{a_1} [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{H}^+] + K_{a_1} + K_{a_1} K_{\text{OS}} [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{T}}} \quad (14)$$

where [H₂A]_T is either nicotinic acid or pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid total.

Rearrangement of eqn. (14) yields eqn. (15),

$$1/k_{\text{obs}} = 1/k_{\text{an}} + ([\text{H}^+] + K_{\text{a}_1}) / k_{\text{an}} K_{\text{a}_1} K_{\text{OS}} [\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{T}} \quad (15)$$

The above mechanism was tested by plotting k_{obs}^{-1} against $[\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{T}}^{-1}$. The plots are linear ($r = 0.99$) for both pyridine-3-carboxylic acid and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid. The k_{an} and K_{OS} for both the reaction determined from the intercept and slope of the above plots, are listed in Table 2. It is generally accepted that complex formation by metal ions proceeds by a mechanism in which the rate-determining step is the change from outer-sphere complex to an inner-sphere complex, preceded by the formation of the outer-sphere complex between the metal ion and ligand. Whether the interchange mechanism of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ is I_{a} or I_{d} remains to be determined.

Table 2. Comparison of anation rate constants (k_{an}) and outer-sphere association constant (k_{OS}) of various amino acids

System	k_{an} s^{-1}	k_{OS}	Ref.
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -H ₂ O ¹⁸	4.17×10^{-6}		1
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -glycine	3.34×10^{-4}		1
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -glycine	6.80×10^{-4}		3
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -alanine	0.58×10^{-4}		2
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -valine	2.34×10^{-4}	3.29 ± 0.10	1
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -L-lysine	1.30×10^{-4}	8.20	4
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -antranilic acid	66.00×10^{-4}		1
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -salysilic acid	17.82×10^{-4}		2
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -L-cysteine	1.28×10^{-4}	9.09	2
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -pyridine-3-carboxylic acid	$(10.24 \pm 0.53) \times 10^{-4}$	5.42 ± 0.83	Present work
Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ -pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid	$(13.79 \pm 0.95) \times 10^{-4}$	18.11 ± 1.98	Present work

The reaction path can be assigned I_{a} or I_{d} if k_{an} is greater or less than the isotopic exchange rate constants¹², for $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$. The far greater values of k_{an} compared to that of k_{ex} support the proposition that the anation of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ by pyridine-3-carboxylic acid or by pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid follows an I_{a} mechanism.

Experimental

Solutions of Cr^{3+} were prepared from $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (G.R.) and dilute nitric acid was added to the stock solution to make it acidic ($[\text{H}^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The solution was standardized by an ion exchange³ and gravimetric method¹³. All the chemicals were either analytical or reagent grade

(B.D.H.). Pyridine-3-carboxylic acid and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid were used as such. The ionic strength of the solutions were adjusted to 0.5 mol dm^{-3} using KNO_3 . The pH was measured on a Nucleonix pH meter having combined glass/Ag-AgCl electrode and standardized¹⁴. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer with 10 mm-matched quartz cells. All calculations were made by a linear least-squares computer program written in BASIC for an Apple II GS PC.

Rate measurements : The kinetics of the complexation of aquachromium(III) with the pyridine carboxylic acids were investigated at 35° with $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. In a typical run, solutions containing the required amount of pyridine carboxylic acid, HNO_3 or NaOH (for maintaining the desired pH) and KNO_3 (to adjust ionic strength) were thermally equilibrated. Then the desired amount Cr^{3+} solution (also thermally equilibrated) was added to the pyridine carboxylic acid solution and mixed in an inert atmosphere (nitrogen). The progress of the reaction was monitored at 570 nm. Pseudo-first order conditions were maintained throughout using a large excess (five-fold) of pyridine carboxylic acid. The rate constants (k_{obs}) were obtained from the slopes of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ vs t plots,

$$\ln(A_\infty - A_t) = \ln(A_\infty - A_0) - k_{\text{obs}} t$$

where A_0 , A_t , A_∞ are the absorbances of the reaction at the beginning, at time t and at equilibrium, respectively. The pseudo-first order rate constants were also calculated using a least-square computer program. There was good agreement between the two values.

Analysis of the products : A mixture of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (0.01 mol) and pyridine-3-carboxylic acid, pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (each 0.02 mol) at pH ~ 3.4 was heated over a water-bath for ~ 3 h. Then small volume of CH_3OH was added and the concentrated solution was left overnight in deep freeze. The resulting crystals were washed with $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and diethyl ether. Cr was estimated by converting Cr^{III} to Cr^{VI} and then estimating Cr^{VI} iodometrically. Nitrogen was estimated by improved Kjeldahl's method using Hoskin's apparatus.

The UV-visible spectra of the products were taken in aqueous medium. The peak corresponding to Cr^{III} at 575 nm retains its existence (as for the reaction mixture at ∞ time and experimental pH) with substantial increase in absorbance, whereas the peak at 410 nm undergoes a shift 20–30 nm ascertaining the formation of a new species¹⁵.

IR spectra (KBr) were taken in a Perkin-Elmer Paragon 500 FT-IR spectrophotometer. For the first product (Fig.

1a) some of the characteristic peaks of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and nicotinic acid still assumed its identity even after coordination. The infrared stretching frequencies associated with the carboxylato portion of the ligand were observed at 1388 cm^{-1} and further at 1558 cm^{-1} with a 24 cm^{-1} downshift from 1582 cm^{-1} (for free nicotinic acid) indicates reduction in force constant of carboxylato group upon ligation through O-atom¹⁶. Sharp peaks at 652 cm^{-1} (in-plane ring deformation) and 460 cm^{-1} (out-of-plane deformation) are attributed to upward shift of characteristic frequencies ($640, 405\text{ cm}^{-1}$) for metal pyridine complexes¹⁶. A 77 cm^{-1} downshift from 1710 to 1633 cm^{-1} for $\nu_{\text{str}}(\text{C}=\text{N})$ again establishes the coordination through N atom. Substantial downward shift in ring stretching vibration from $1641, 1481\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for free nicotinic acid to $1539, 1419\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively confirms coordination of pyridine-3-carboxylic acid through conjugation. Broad peaks at $3618, 3655, 3381\text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to $\nu_{\text{str}}(\text{O}-\text{H})$ of aquo- Cr^{III} complex. The 1789 cm^{-1} peak corresponds to proton transfer in nicotinic acid¹⁷. The $\nu_{\text{def}}(\text{O}-\text{H})$ at 1634 cm^{-1} , $\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ at 551 and ρ_{MO} at 494 cm^{-1} of aquo- Cr^{III} complex still retained its identity. Water stretches at 825 and 592 cm^{-1} were also observed indicating that water molecules occupy the remaining sites of the substituted complex. From the above correlated data it may be inferred that the product is $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_4(\text{L})](\text{NO}_3)_2$.

For the second product (Fig. 1b), the $\nu_{\text{str}}(\text{O}-\text{H})$ at $3549, 3425\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the existence of free carboxyl group of pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid ligand and signifies that ligation is through one carboxylato oxygen and one ring nitrogen. The ligation through carboxylato oxygen is confirmed by decrease in $\nu_{\text{str}}(\text{C}=\text{O})$ from 1575 to 1555 cm^{-1} and a peak at 1385 cm^{-1} . Coordination through ring nitrogen is confirmed by decrease in $\nu_{\text{str}}(\text{C}=\text{N})$ from 1697 to 1685 cm^{-1} . The $\nu_{\text{str}}(\text{O}-\text{H})$ and $\nu_{\text{def}}(\text{O}-\text{H})$ at 3388 and 1640 cm^{-1} in the said aquo-product is concomitant with literature. Sharp peaks at $647, 463\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with an upward shift indicate the metal pyridine coordination¹⁶. Further, peaks at $825, 586\text{ cm}^{-1}$ confirm the occupation of remaining sites by coordinated water¹⁵. Hence, from the above data the product may be inferred as $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_4(\text{L})](\text{NO}_3)_2$.

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References

1. A. Khan and Kabir-ud-Din, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 1082; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 98; I. A. Khan, M. Shahid and Kabir-ud-Din, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 382; S. C. Tyagi and A. A. Khan, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 1899.
2. I. A. Khan and Kabir-ud-Din, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1985, **17**, 1263; I. A. Khan, M. Shahid and Kabir-ud-Din, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1990, **27**, 101; G. J. Khan and Kabir-ud-Din, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1992, **26**, 351; Kabir-ud-Din, I. A. Khan and M. Shahid, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 864.
3. D. Banerjee and S. D. Chaudhuri, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 871.
4. G. J. Khan and Kabir-ud-Din, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1995, **107**, 11.
5. M. A. Abdullah, J. Barrett and P. O. Brein, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 1647; B. K. Niogy and G. S. De, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1983, **92**, 153; B. K. Niogy and G. S. De, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 208; R. E. Hamm, R. L. Johnson, R. N. Perkins and R. E. Davis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4469; J. K. Dei, N. N. Pasupalak and P. Mohanty, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1997, **22**, 516.
6. C. H. Langford and H. B. Gray, "Ligand Substitution Processes", W. A. Benjamin, New York, 1965.
7. G. B. Purser and E. L. King, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 392.
8. C. Postmus and L. E. King, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 1208.
9. A. E. Martell and R. M. Smith, "Critical Stability Constants: Amino Acids", Plenum Press, New York, 1974, Vol. 1.
10. T. Ramasami and A. G. Sykes, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 2885.
11. F. Basolo and R. G. Pearson, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", 2nd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1953, Chap. 6.
12. T. W. Swaddle, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **14**, 217; J. H. Espenson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 1554.
13. A. I. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1962.
14. D. D. Perrin and B. Dempsey, "Buffers for pH and Metal Ion Control", Chapman and Hall, London, 1974.
15. G. B. Purser and E. L. King, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 394.
16. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compound", 4th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1997, Part B.
17. C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical Application of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic, London.